

28-CH₃), 0.68 (3H, s, 18-CH₃), with those of dihydrobrassicasterol and its acetate⁸ revealed its identity as dihydrobrassicasterol (1). The mass fragmentation of its acetate⁸ showed no molecular ion peak but peaks at *m/z* 382 (*M*⁺-60, 100), 367 (17.97), 255 (*M*⁺-60-C₉H₁₆, 18) and 213 (14.91), which further supported its structure.

1; R=H
1a; R=COCH₃

2; R=H
2a; R=COCH₃

Compound B analysed for C₁₁H₁₆O₃, *M*⁺ 196 (15.4%), showed uv (EtOH) absorption at 220 nm for an α,β-unsaturated lactone. Its ir spectrum (KBr) showed bands at 3 445 (OH), 1 740 and 1 625 (α,β-unsaturated-γ-lactone) and 1 380–1 400 cm⁻¹ (*gem*-dimethyls). It gave a monoacetate (2a) (Ac₂O/Py), m.p. 86°. A comparison of its ¹H nmr spectrum δ (90 MHz, CDCl₃) 5.62 (1H, s, olefinic proton), 4.28 (1H, m, C₁-H), 1.76 (3H, s, 3-Me), 1.45 (3H, s, 5α-Me), 1.25 (3H, s, 5β-Me), 2.8 (1H, m, 2α-H), 2.0 (1H, m, 2β-H), 1.70 (1H, m, 6α-H) and 1.4 (1H, m, 6β-H), and other physical and spectral characteristics with those of loliolide, suggested the possible identity which was confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample⁵.

Loliolide has hitherto been reported from plant sources, e.g. from a terrestrial plant *Digitalis purpurea*⁴ and a marine alga, *Padina tetrastrumata* Hauck⁵. It was also reported from *Dolabella ecaudata*⁶ (a sea hare), not very surprisingly, for sea hares are herbivorous and concentrate and store selected algal metabolites in digestive gland from which the metabolites are slowly released⁷. However, its present isolation from a marine animal, a zoanthid of *Gemmaria* sp. appears to be first of its kind.

Experimental

The cleaned animals (7 kg) were percolated with rectified spirit (3 × 5 dm³) and the combined extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to a predominantly aqueous suspension (2 dm³). The aqueous concentrate was repeatedly extracted with ether (12 × 50 ml). Evaporation of the ether solvent left a dark green gummy material (10 g), which was

absorbed over silica gel (50 g) and chromatographed over a silica gel (100–200 mesh, 200 g) column using solvents of increasing polarity.

Evaporation of n-hexane–benzene (9:1) fractions left colourless solid, compound A, which was crystallised from methanol as shining needles (2 g), m.p. 148–49°; [α]_D -27.2°; *R*_f 0.52 (C₆H₆-EtOAc, 9:1). Evaporation of benzene-ethyl acetate (95:5) fractions yielded a colourless solid compound B, which was crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (150 mg), m.p. 151°; [α]_D -99.0°; *R*_f 0.4 (EtOAc).

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Phenylpropenoid Constituents of *Cymbopogon microstachys*

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CYMOPOGON microstachys (Hook. f.) S. Soenarko has natural occurrence in the Himalayan foothills. This is the first report on existence of this species in this region. Also, no work has been reported on this species so far. The confirmation of the identification has been done by S. Soenarko (who raised this species) in R.B.G., Kew (Herbarium

No. H/5/88). Our results present useful constituents.

C. microstachys is considered to be intermediate between *C. flexuosus* and *C. khasianus*. *C. microstachys* is separated from *C. flexuosus* as it has deflected raceme, a narrow spatulate panicle and the lower glume of the sessile spikelet is slightly concave at the base, and differs from *C. khasianus* by having a shorter raceme, shorter sessile spikelet and narrowly winged lower glume of the sessile spikelet. *C. microstachys* can be confused with *C. calciphilus*, but the latter usually has bearded nodes, tomentose basal sheaths and bearded triangular patches¹. *C. flexuosus* and *C. khasianus* are sources of citral (60–80%), geraniol, nerol and their esters^{2,3}. We observed that *C. microstachys*, on the other hand, has methyleugenol, elemicin, methylisoeugenol and isoelemicin as major compounds (60%), while citral, geraniol, nerol or their esters were not noticed in its essential oil.

The comparison of the constituents of the essential oil of *C. flexuosus* and *C. khasianus* with those of *C. microstachys* provides simple chemical basis for identification.

Experimental

Isolation of 1, 3 and 4: Aerial parts of freshly collected plant material (5 kg) were finely chopped and steam-distilled. The essential oil was extracted from the NaCl-saturated distillate and concentrated by distillation. Removal of the last traces of solvent at reduced pressure left 15 g (0.3%) of essential oil. The major compounds were isolated by flash chromatography (SiO₂, hexane-ether) and separated on a μ -Porasil semiprep hplc column using hexane-ether (9 : 1) as the mobile phase. The ir, mass and ¹H nmr spectra were recorded and compared with the literature reports^{4–7}. The GC-MS of the oil was undertaken as discussed earlier⁸.

Results and Discussion

The compounds 1, 3 and 4 were identified as methyleugenol, elemicin and isoelemicin, respectively on the basis of ir, mass and specially ¹H nmr spectral data⁴.

- 1; R₁=H, R₂=R₃=OCH₃, R₄=CH₂-CH=OH₂ (Methyleugenol)
 2; R₁=H, R₂=R₃=OCH₃, R₄=CH=CH-CH₃ (Methylisoeugenol)
 3; R₁=R₂=R₃=OCH₃, R₄=CH₂-CH=OH₂ (Elemicin)
 4; R₁=R₂=R₃=OCH₃, R₄=CH=CH-OH₂ (Isoelemicin)
 5; R₁=H, R₂=R₃=OCH₃, R₄=CHO (Veratraldehyde)
 6; R₁=R₂=R₃=OCH₃, R₄=CHO (3,4,5-Trimethoxybenzaldehyde)

GC-MS study of the essential oil from *C. microstachys* indicated the presence of more than 45 compounds; 31 of these have been identified and are given in Table 1. Most of the unidentified compounds are present in traces or in low concentration. Phenylpropenoids, viz. methyleugenol, elemicin, isoelemicin and methylisoeugenol constitute 60% and two di- and trimethoxy benzaldehydes make 2% of the oil. Monoterpene alcohols linalool and α -terpineol make 4.6% of the oil. Among the hydrocarbons (19.5%) limonene is the single major compound (9.3%) and five sesquiterpene hydrocarbons make 2.9%. Other minor compounds include epoxy compounds (2%).

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF ESSENTIAL OIL OF *C. microstachys*

Compd.	Content %
Tricyclene	0.6
α -Pinene	2.0
Camphene	3.2
Sabinene	0.2
β -Myrcene	0.4
Limonene	9.8
β -Phellandrene	0.2
cis-Limonene oxide	1.6
trans-Ocimene	0.7
6-Methyl-5-hepten-2-one	0.1
cis-3-Hexenol	0.1
4-Nonanone	0.4
3,4-Epoxy-3,7-di-methyl-1,6-octadiene	0.2
6,7-Epoxy-3,7-di-methyl-1,3-octadiene	0.2
Linalool	3.2
Terpinen-4-ol	0.2
Caryophyllene	0.3
α -Terpineol	1.2
Carvotanacetone	0.1
allo-Aromadenrene	0.2
Humulene	0.1
Aromadadrene	1.7
trans- α -Bergamotene	0.6
Methyleugenol	19.5
Caryophyllene oxide	0.5
Nerolidol	0.4
Methylisoeugenol	4.2
Elemicin	25.3
Veratraldehyde	1.0
Isoelemicin	11.0
3,4,5-Trimethoxybenzaldehyde	1.0
Unidentified	10.3

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Fatty Acid Composition of *Fleurya interrupta* and *Ajuga macrosperma*

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As a part of our programme to explore the herbal drugs, we reported¹ the presence of a good number of amino acids from two endemic herbs of Tripura, *Fleurya interrupta* Gaudich (*Urticaceae*) and *Ajuga macrosperma* Wall (*Labiatae*). Now we report the fatty acid composition of these plants.

The ground aerial parts (150 g) of the young plant of *F. interrupta* were extracted with petrol (b.p. 60–80°) by percolation method and the crude petrol extract was column chromatographed through silica gel to get an oil (0.9 g). The oil was saponified and the fatty acid mixture (0.4 g) was recovered in the usual manner, esterified with diazomethane and the resulting Me-esters were purified by passing through a silica gel column and analysed by glc technique. The components were identified² by comparing their retention times with those of the authentic samples in both 10% DEGS and 10% PEGA columns. The relative percentage abundances of the component fatty acids as calculated from the recorded peak areas of their Me-esters were as follows: 14:0 (8.22), 14:1 (5.61), 14:2 (5.16), 16:0 (24.5), 16:1 (3.82), 18:0 (5.13), 18:1 (9.55), 18:2 (2.5), 20:0 (1.75), 22:5 (3.2) and others unidentified (30.56%). The presence of unsaturated fatty acids was also confirmed by catalytic hydrogenation of a part of Me-ester mixture with 10% Pd–C followed by glc analysis of the hydrogenated product.

The plant *A. macrosperma* (300 g) was worked up in a similar manner, and the component fatty acids along with their relative percentage abundance determined were as follows: 12:0 (0.29), 12:1 (0.38), 14:0 (0.98), 14:2 (6.12), 16:0 (7.34), 16:1 (13.71), 16:2 (11.42), 18:0 (11.97), 18:1 (7.48), 18:2 (6.75), 18:3 (5.39), 20:1 (7.83), 20:2 (9.83), 22:0 (0.97), 22:1 (0.91) and others unidentified (8.63%).

The presence of unsaturated fatty acids was also confirmed in a similar manner as before.

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Fatty Acid Composition of Minor Seed Oils

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In continuation¹ of our screening programme of the seed oils, a study of six seed oils belonging to *Acrocarpus fraxinifolius*, *Casuarina equisetifolia*, *Legerstroemia therolli*, *Prosopis juliflora*, *Boerhaavia defusa* and *Dyospyros cardifolia* are reported and fatty acid composition of these oil-seeds are determined by glc.

The ground seeds were extracted with light petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) in a Soxhlet to afford the oil. Analytical values of seed oils were determined according to the procedures recommended by the AOCS² (Table 1). All the oils and their esters showed no conjugation or *trans*-unsaturation or any other functional groups in uv and ir studies. The quantitative examination of methyl esters was undertaken by glc. Identification of each acid was made by comparing its retention time with those of the standard samples of fatty acid methyl esters (Sigma and groundnut oil methyl esters).

The seed oil of *A. fraxinifolius* contains high percentage of oleic acid (76.3%). *C. equisetifolia* contains an unusual amount (78.5%) of essential fatty acid, i.e. linoleic acid. The seed oil compositional data indicate that the oils of *L. therolli* and *P. juliflora* contain palmitic acid in amount of 23.5 and 27.1%, respectively.

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